

SOME OPINIONS ABOUT HOW TO MAKE YOUNG PUPILS INTERESTED IN LEARNING

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Annotation: In the article were discussed opinions how to make young pupils interested in learning. Internal and external motivation of learners are explained.

Key words: teaching, learning, motivation, internal motivation, external motivation, young pupils.

Today, it is very important for all pedagogues how to make young learners interested in reading. The reason for this is that our children are learning many things through the Internet from a young age than us. Therefore, in the article, we want to think about why encouraging learners with prizes does not work, and what should be done instead.

We are going to speak about internal and external motivation of learners.

We rarely think about intrinsic motivation. One word is enough to explain our sincere desires, our situation - "I want". Children willingly listen to their favorite band, make something with their own hands, or read adventure novels because they enjoy doing it.

Extrinsic motivation varies from pocket money to school grades. This can be explained by one sentence: "If you do this, you will get this."

Psychologist Alfie Kohn warns not only parents, but also teachers against the use of various incentives in the book *Punishment with Rewards*. Some parents promise to take their child to the zoo so that they can study well, others buy expensive gadgets and even give money. The problem is that this method does not work: the learner will continue to study like this, and on top of that, he will be upset with his loved ones because he did not get what he was promised!

Teachers try to increase enthusiasm in seemingly noble ways: they introduce various statuses (the best learner of the month), they create benefits for good

learners. This is often the case: the best learner of the month is usually one learner, and the awards are usually given to a group of learners who do not change the composition. The rest of the learners feel unlucky.

Why does increasing extrinsic motivation not work?

When we say, "If you do this, you will get this," the child will initially accept the promise with enthusiasm. At the same time, the instinct of self-protection also comes into play.

The child begins to look for the most reliable and shortest way, not the creative way to solve the problem.

He asks himself the question: "Why should I take the risk and write the control work myself? It's better if I copy from the experts, it's more reliable." You see, the goals change: not studying for knowledge, but studying for rewards.

Extrinsic motivation can work great, but only in conjunction with intrinsic. He doesn't move forward by himself, he just "gets the job done" and forces him to get what he wants faster.

What influences interest in reading?

Kohn distinguishes three factors that influence motivation:

1. Young children are ready to learn and they do not require anything for it. They have a strong internal motivation: they study because it is interesting to them.

2. Children who can maintain internal motivation study effectively. Others think they can't do it, but that's not the case. Although some schoolchildren get only low grades, they show themselves positively in other areas. For example, they know dozens of songs of their favorite singer by heart (in mathematics, they cannot remember the multiplication table). Or they read fiction with passion (they don't touch the classics). They are interested in that. That is the essence of intrinsic motivation.

3. Perks destroy intrinsic motivation

Psychologists Carol Ames and Carol Dueck found that when parents and teachers emphasize a privilege, children's interest immediately fades.

Where to start?

Returning motivation to study is a long process, and its success depends mainly on the parents. Adults need to focus on three things: content, cooperation, and freedom of choice.

1. Content. When the child does not comply with our request, we look for ways to influence his behavior. Better yet, think about how reasonable your request is. If your child doesn't get only "4s" and "5s" in physics, there is nothing to worry about. Children refuse our request to "not make noise" not because they are "deaf", but because of the psychological characteristics of their age.

2. Cooperation. Unfortunately, in the context of communication with a child, this word is unfamiliar to many parents. However, the older your children are, the more you should involve them in cooperation. It is necessary to discuss, explain, make plans together. Try to talk to the child like an adult. The dream of a 15-year-old boy to become an astronaut should not be ignored. Sit down and explain why this is impossible. Perhaps your son will find inner motivation to grow from your words.

3. Freedom of choice. The child must feel like a part of the process, so that he takes responsibility for finding a solution to the problem. If your child starts to misbehave, ask him why. You might say, "I know what that's all about," but give it a try. Perhaps his answer will surprise you.

We look for internal motivation

It is not easy to correct a child's internal state, however, efforts in this direction can bear fruit.

1. Learn to accept your child. For example, you may not like your daughter's new image, but you have to accept it. In other words, it's about understanding, not pampering.

3. Help the child come to a conclusion about his purpose in life. Often there is no internal motivation, because the child does not understand why these formulas, endless rules and theorems are needed. It is important that you decide what your child wants to do after school. Long conversations with parents, career advice and books for teenagers help to understand this.

4. Build the learning process on the child's interests. When studying, you should try to combine the child's sincere interests (internal motivation) with school lessons. This process requires a lot of attention from the individual and the parents. For example, you can learn English by watching your favorite movie. A teenager who loves computer games should be interested in programming and related knowledge.

One of the most important tasks is to draw out internal motivation from the child. This is not a problem for a parent who is smart, wise, and sincerely interested in his child's life.

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